

The Role of Digital Library in Higher Education in India

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Abstract

Digital Library encourages the thinking process and offers the resources, creativity, and investigation which make learning more easy and fruitful. The main function of today's modern library is to provide references, periodicals, textbooks and helpful to students, teachers and researchers of various subjects and streams. The purpose of present paper is to study the role of digital library in India. To study the various digital platforms and important measures taken by the national organizations/agencies to develop academic libraries and its quality of services the following studies takes place.

Key words: Digital, libraries, Information, Technology, Researchers.

Introduction

The library is regarded as an integral part and heart of an institution/organisation. To improve the quality and infrastructure of academic libraries in India, national organisations like Government of India MHRD (Ministry of Human Resource Development), UGC (University Grants Commission), NAAC (National Assessment and Accreditation Council), NKC (National Knowledge Commission), and various other educational commissions provide important guidelines for the academic libraries in India to measure the quality of higher education in India.

In today's world most of the subjects are multidisciplinary and users or students are guided to the self-learning environment where a well equipped library can provide them to go in the depth of the subject and to gain more advanced knowledge. Various digital platforms have been made available by MHRD (Ministry of Human Resource Development) for digital reading.

The library since long time has been considered to be the source power of knowledge and also as a base of knowledge. In higher education and research, the library has specific functions to facilitate the extensive use of learning resources by students, researchers and teachers. With the growth of literature in large amount even in the same field, this group of libraries users has faced problems in identifying the appropriate literature for their use and consultation in a desired timeframe.

Information and Communication Technology (ICT), particularly during the last two decades, has significantly contributed to open the door of accessing, hidden knowledge in a highly efficient manner. Initially Information and Communication Technology was used in the library environment for developing databases information resources mainly aiming at storing and retrieving. Information on various types of publication resources and also to organize various types of information services the ICT has put us in the electronic environment to help identifying, assessing, acquiring, recording, organising, and disseminating information and information resources.

According to Wikipedia "A digital library is a library in which collection are stored in digital formats as opposed to print, microform, or other media and accessible by computers. The digital content may be stored locally, or accessed remotely via computer networks. A digital library is a type of information retrieval system. The first use of the term digital library in print may have been in a 1988 report to the Corporation for National Research Initiatives."

A digital library is also named as an online library, a digital repository, internet library or a digital collection is an online database of digital objects that can include text, audio, video, images, digital documents or many other digital media formats or a library easily accessible through the internet.

Advantages of Digital Library were as follows:

- Preserve the valuable documents, rare and special collections of libraries, archives and museums,
- Provide faster access to the holding of libraries worldwide through automated catalogues,
- Helps to locate both physical and digitized versions of scholarly articles and books through single interface.

Limitations of digital library were as follows:

- Digital libraries cannot possibly replace the environment of a physical library as we still like to see and browse reading materials physically and get attracted more to read,
- Lack of skills in handling computer viruses and lack of standardization for digitized materials are important limitations, while there are many benefits of digitization,
- Major problem is, however, ensuring the readers with the quality of digitized materials,

Review of Literature

Mehta, D., & Wang, X. (2020), The purpose of this paper is to share the experience of a university library in acknowledgement to the COVID-19 pandemic since early March 2020. The paper defines the library's position during the crisis and depicts the uncharted challenges that the pandemic has posed to its digital services. This paper aims to make other university libraries aware of what the library has furnished with providing digital services to its teaching faculty and students during the pandemic. It also describes the challenges and significance for the library professionals working in house and remotely.

Oswal, S. K. (2014), The author provides a detailed analysis of the different condition of convenience issues in digital databases under several headers with a special focus on full-text PDF files. The researcher also highlight that long-term studies with actual, blind screen reader users employing both qualitative and computerized research tools can yield relevant data for the designers and developers to improve these databases to a level that they begin to provide an equal approach.

Varatharajan, N., & Chandrashekara, M. (2007), The researcher here states that digital libraries and digitization are essential for publish and preserving knowledge. Digital library activities are meeting momentum in developing countries, especially India. Since most higher education and research institutions in India are funded and controlled by the central and state governments, clear-cut national plans and policies are needed for framework, standards, metadata, incomparability, multilingual databases, training, co-ordination, copyright, and archiving and preservation methods, so that our heritage of knowledge and culture can be the ruin of time and present and future generations can benefit and be guided by them.

Jeevan, V. K. J. (2004), Digital libraries aim at linear access to content over computer and communication networks, and digitization may be taken as a visible overture to enhance the shelf life of non-digital content by storage apart from the ethic of increased and easy access, thereby facilitate usage. As a fresh, lively and dynamic area with a lot of devotion and activity by researchers from different disciplines, institutions and countries, digital libraries are viewed in different perspectives and the single most development that has brought about comprehensive changes in the library and information development currently in the developed world is that of digital libraries portrayed by the researcher.

Impact of digital library in higher education

In Higher Education the quality and access has been a subject of intense concern to all in the world. Higher Education has also received a major push with the use of digital technologies in all aspects in

India. This in turn helps the quality improvement and accessibility of Higher Education to large part of students as well as up skilling of the teachers across the India. Digital technologies have also greatly ingrained the management and governance of the institutions as well as authorization and ranking of the Higher Education Institutions all over the world. Department of Higher Education, Ministry of Human Resource Development, has undertaken many initiatives for exploiting the digital technologies in improving the quality and accessibility in Higher Education in India.

To improve the learning outcomes and improve the access and quality of learning, technology offers solutions, in the form of digital education, National Mission on Education through Information and Communication Technology, is a major initiative of Ministry of Human Resource Development to animate digital education solutions to improve the access to quality contents and also to improve the research outcomes.

Various initiatives have been taken up under NMEICT programme, the major currently ongoing initiatives like SWAYAM (Study Webs of Active Learning For Young Aspiring Minds), SWAYAM Prabha, National Digital Library (NDL), e- Yantra, FOSSE, Spoken Tutorials, and Virtual Labs has been armed by various higher educational institutions.

Various digital platforms have been made available by MHRD for digital reading for higher education students, teachers and researchers such as: Shodhganga: It is a digital repository for research scholars across universities and institutes to deposit, re-use and share their dissertations and thesis in digital formats. It is an open access to the world-wide academic community. The Shodhganga repository has grown to a formidable size of 2,32,556 thesis as on date with a progressive growth in last few years. An average from more than 397 universities of India. Approximately 40,000 thesis are getting submitted every year.

Shodhgangotri: Under shodhgangotri drive research scholars/research supervisors in universities could deposit an electronic version of approved synopsis submitted by research scholars to the universities for registering themselves under the Ph.D programme. Synopsis in shodhgangotri would later be graphed to full-text thesis in Shodhganga.

National Digital Library (NDL): To make accessible to the learners community learning resources through a single-window National Mission on Education through Information and Communication Technology has approved the National Digital Library of India project and resolved funding through Ministry of Education, Government of India.

INFLIBNET: The INFLIBNET library plays a vital role in the collection development and publication of scientific and technical information to meet the present and future needs of the centre. The INFLIBNET centre has a small, specialised library consisting of 2000 documents on computer communication, information and library science. By using SOUL integrated library management software the library will become fully computerized. The collection of the library is available online through the web OPAC facility of the SOUL. The INFLIBNET library plays a vital role in the collection, development and publication of scientific and technical information to meet the present and prospect needs of the centre.

Soul 3.0: The centre has taken-up a number of actions for the benefit of the academic community as the technology being a driving force in the contemporary education system in India. These drives are designated into various phenomenon. The SOUL 3.0 (Software for University Libraries) is state-of-the-art integrated library management software designed and advanced by the INFLIBNET centre based on requirements of colleges, universities and other academic libraries. For bibliographic formats and circulation protocols the software is compliant to international standards. It is compliant to international standards such as MARC21 for the bibliographic format, Unicode based Universal Character Sets for multilingual bibliographic records and NCIP2.0 and SIP2 based protocols for RFID, electronic surveillance and control.

E-Shodhsindhu: is an initiative of Consortium for Higher Education Electronic Resources by Ministry of Education, Government of India. It provides access to eresources (10000+full text journals,

164300+e-books and 4 databases through e- Shodhsindhu and 600000 e-books through National Digital Library) to universities, colleges and centrally funded technical institutions in India.

N-List:“National Library and Information Services Infrastructure project for scholarly content, graduated as a regular scheme of UGC under UGC-Info net Digital Library Consortium as college component, is united into e-Shodhsindhu: Consortia for Higher Education e-resources. The N-List provides access to 6000+journals, 1,64,300+e-books, under N-List and 6,00,000 e-books through National Digital Library to all Government, Government-Aided as well as non-aided colleges through a proxy server/shibboleth.

Conclusion

Summing up it is found that during the Covid-19 pandemic, libraries and higher education institutions have launched digital papers projects to document life during the pandemic. Thus by creating a digital, cultural record of collective memories from the period researchers have also utilized digital archiving to create specialized research databases. India is so rich in content of indigenous research and development in disciplines varied from science and technology to social science, humanities and spirituality, there is tremendous need for presenting fully cultivated digital libraries by appropriately tagging the content with affordable information technology.

The software boom encompass the country, as a result of the big leap in computer penetration, sudden rise in proficient manpower, and sizable improvement in communication infrastructure should also be treated as an asset and taken advantage of by authorities and information professionals to create and maintain digital information facilities to guide in the new information age.

In addition to offering many benefits, various obstructions found in the digital libraries such as facilities problems, digitizing collections, copyrights, human resource, and cost issues. These obstacles become challenges for universities who apply digital libraries. Compared to conventional libraries, digital libraries provide more benefits for each user, student, teacher or researcher in higher education in India.

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